

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NAMBORO KETTE****FIRST NAME: ISSA OMER****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MSWord -Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The process of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
3. Punctuationsand language variants (EUCLID 2021, 15-22; 24-32)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The lessons learned in period one as part of the first material of study, "International Academic Writing," that I have just completed allowed me to understand some useful details and to consolidate my knowledge in academic essay writing.

Very significant in learning the fundamental rules of writing a good academic essay, these lessons learned represent for me a major gain, both in terms of mastering computer tools (word, format a document, use Zotero for different styles of text) and the good practices and methodologies to write a good academic essay. After going through ACA-401D, I have come to the conclusion that the lessons contained in its pages have provided me with the useful fundamental tools which will help me to follow this doctoral program in which I am engaged for the next two or three years, complying with the rules enacted by EUCLID University.

This assignment, it will show what I have been able to retain and understand from different lessons that I have learned, those that constitute the corpus of rules that govern the writing of a good academic dissertation.

2) THE PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

There are several types of essay writing, but an academic essay or scholarly writing differs from the others, first of all by the fact that it is a work carried out in the academic context on the background of the non-fictional character. Examples of academic essay writing are numerous; they may include research results or reports on empirical fieldwork that may or may not be published in journals; books, reports, or other periodicals (or remain in manuscript, thesis, or dissertation form); monographs; conference documents; literature reviews; Explanations; technical reports; Translations; presentation of students; as well as undergraduate versions on the above (EUCLID 2021, 7). It seeks to provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate evidence-based ideas. Thus, the next important thing after understanding the topic is reading and researching what to write. Reading and researching will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer the question. What do you already know about this subject? What do you need to read and know to write the essay? Is what you read useful for your topic? Can you use it to support the answers? These are the kinds of questions you have to ask yourself when you read to write an essay (EUCLID 2021, 8).

It is essential to make some notes while you read, as this will be the basis for your essay. However, in your initial reading, you should underline or highlight relevant information, which you can return to when you re-read and take notes. Therefore, spend much time looking for relevant information (such as summaries, direct quotes from texts, useful examples, case studies, or statistics). The notes should come from any information source, including copying the bibliographic details or everything you read. Include the author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication, and other relevant details (EUCLID 2021, 8-9). This is the best way that can help you write your academic essay. However, from the triggering of the writing to the handling of your work, the writer must follow and methodically apply the necessary steps that are crucial for his writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14).

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAY

Fundamentally, the structure of an essay is based on the three main parts that compose it: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). In the introduction, the writer must begin with a general idea to introduce the topic. After that, he poses the problem raised by the topic's question and gives a brief answer to it. This first part of the essay, usually ends by showing the plan. In the body essay, we have all the main ideas, including secondary ideas, arguments, and all means to support ideas. The lesson learned is that one part of the body is for one idea. The last thing in the structure of an academic essay is the conclusion. It is the moment to restate the position about the problem raised by the topic's question. At this point, the writer can also go through the opening question. These three parts of the essay are mandatory. But, the writer has to know that it is important to follow certain steps methodically to produce a good essay. These steps are as follows (EUCLID 2021, 7-14) :

4) STARTING THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

The drafting steps are not rigidly linear. However, of course, some basic steps are considered when writing academic essays. They should be undertaken before starting. It is called early start-up: it is best to start as early as possible. One of the first things required to write is to have enough time to read, research, think, and write. It is always advisable to be active. Define the question and analyze the task: Although defining and writing everything you know about a topic, analyzing and presenting the answers to the question is key. Think of it this way: what will be lost if you do not answer your question? You will look “Good enough to start but not to finish” because eventually, your readers will want an answer beyond Just curious (Turabian et al. 2018, 21). Writing an initial plan: Having a plan to go on an academic essay is very important. This should include your initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic. If a writing plan is written correctly, it will help you determine how you will answer the question and the type of information to be used.

a) MAKE RESEARCH ON THE TOPIC

Fundamentally, writing an academic essay must be serious work. For this, it is important that the writer can have a good organization. So, after understanding the subject, the next important step is also to read and research what to write. This will provide the knowledge and evidence needed to develop a thesis and an answer. Also, while reading the subject, it is necessary to ask the following questions: What do I know about the subject? What do I need to read and know to write the essay? Is this material useful for this/argument? Can I use this material to support the answers and arguments?

While reading, it is important to take notes; this is the fundamental element in the organization of the means as a prelude to the writing of the essay. During reading, always keep the topic clearly in mind and know that solid evidence must be used to support the arguments. Therefore, spend a lot of time researching relevant information (such as summaries, direct citations of texts, useful examples, case studies, or statistics).

Notes must come from any source, including copies of bibliographic details or anything in public literature or readings. Provide the author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication, and other relevant details.

Think of it this way: what will be lost if you do not answer your question? Your answer might be Nothing. I just want to know. Good enough to start but not to finish because eventually, your readers will want an answer beyond Just curious.

b) ORGANISANIZING IDEAS

After reading and researching, your ideas become more developed, and it is at this precise moment that it is time to draft a writing plan that will help you determine how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured. The plan must be prepared to take into account the following: One idea is put in one part, and many arguments come to support the main idea.

c) WRITING THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

This step consists of producing the first draft of the essay according to the structure and framework you would have imagined. The draft is like the raw material of this exercise. It is the best way to produce a good essay. Thus, the details of the essay will become simpler.

d) REFERENCING THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

All academic writings must contain references (EUCLID 2021, 11). Only references protect against plagiarism which is a serious academic offense.

e) EDITING THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

The editing is considerably improved thanks to careful work. It is often recommended to keep the work aside for a while before editing it. This practice gives you the opportunity to think more about your answer and arguments and return to your essay with new perspectives.

f) HANDLING THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

This is the last step. It consists of handing over the essay to the teacher. This implies that the writer must carefully read the guidelines and follow them. Imagine how the tutors/teachers would like the assignments to be presented, and make sure you comply with the requirements. In general, the foregoing remarks should be relied upon to make the work much better.

5) PUNCTUATIONS AND USEFUL RULES FOR WRITING GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

Several rules for using punctuation ensure the good quality of the essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 16-23). By punctuation, we mean all the signs, such as the comma, the semicolon, the period, the parenthesis, the dashes, etc. They give meaning to a sentence, and their misuse gives another meaning or a total misunderstanding of what the sentence wants to express. Another useful rule for writing a good academic essay is about avoiding plagiarism. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of this source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). The ACA-401D course pack – period one, teaches us about how to avoid plagiarism. We can use quotations or paraphrases to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 35).

The lessons learned also teach us that there are some abbreviations and Latin expressions that can be used in English sentences (EUCLID 2021, 59)—for example, etc. A commonly used Latin expressions list is given in the book (EUCLID 2021, 62-64).

6) LANGUAGE VARIANTS

Another lesson learned in this first period is the differences between American and British English. Many examples have been given. These differences can be found in pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar, but they look similar. American English and British English are two variants of Global English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with educated or scientific English. Most of the discrepancies can be attributed to different national histories and cultural development (EUCLID 2021, 25). Thus, as much as there are differences between American English and British English, as well as a wide variety of writers, there are also writing styles. But what is significant for us to remember is that EUCLID recommends the Chicago style model (EUCLID 2021, 41).

7) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that must be consistent (EUCLID 2021, 4). Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. So guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the writer's personal style but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent. A style guide should be an invaluable tool for any writer, but particularly for the freelance writer. Freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication

type they work with. It is important that, as a freelancer, you can demonstrate an ability to follow a prescribed style, but equally that you can learn and record what your customers prefer from their comments. This will help increase your customers' satisfaction in the long term and will help place you as the supplier of choice for written material or assignments (EUCLID 2021, 42).

8) **CONCLUSION**

The lessons learned during this period 1 have been very beneficial. They allowed us to understand the different steps to be followed, the essential rules, as well as the models of other writing styles and the use of both American and British formulas, to be able to acquire the necessary skills, to carry out studies at EUCLID.

However, as a newcomer to the doctoral studies circuit, we must follow and learn with great seriousness the Chicago style manual to prepare ourselves for the challenges that await us during this schooling.

REFERENCE

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